

Production Optimization Strategies for a Gas Field under Declining Reservoir Pressure Conditions

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Abstract:

Declining reservoir pressure is a major challenge affecting gas production sustainability in mature gas reservoirs. This study investigates production optimization strategies for the MnaziBay Gas Field under declining reservoir pressure conditions using an Integrated Production Modelling approach. The gas field is estimated to contain 1036 Bscf of gas reserves produced from the Miocene reservoir formations, and currently operates with five producing wells, MB-1, MB-2, MB-3, MB-4, and MS-1X at a field production rate of 130 MMscfd over a contractual period of 16 years. Four optimization scenarios were investigated, including the existing production system, application of surface compression, perforation of additional reservoir zones, and drilling of infill wells, with reservoir performance, well deliverability, and surface production network behaviour analysed using MBAL, PROSPER, and GAP simulation software. The existing five-well configuration was found capable of maintaining the plateau for only 4.49 years, representing merely 28% of the contractual target. Among the perforation scenarios assessed, the configuration employing 4-inch tubing at a separator pressure of 725 psi yielded the most favourable outcome, extending the plateau duration by 12.54 years, from 6.24 years to 18.78 years, demonstrating the significant potential of accessing additional productive layers.

Keywords: 3-5 Gas Production Optimization, Declining Reservoir Pressure, Integrated Production Modelling, Surface Compression, and Production Sustainability.

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Abstract.

Penurunan tekanan reservoir merupakan tantangan utama yang mempengaruhi keberlanjutan produksi gas di reservoir gas yang sudah matang. Studi ini menyelidiki strategi optimalisasi produksi untuk Lapangan Gas MnaziBay di bawah kondisi tekanan reservoir yang menurun menggunakan pendekatan Pemodelan Produksi Terpadu. Ladang gas diperkirakan mengandung 1036 Bscf cadangan gas yang dihasilkan dari formasi reservoir Miosen, dan saat ini beroperasi dengan lima sumur penghasil, MB-1, MB-2, MB-3, MB-4, dan MS-1X dengan tingkat produksi lapangan 130 MMscfd selama periode kontrak 16 tahun. Empat skenario optimasi diselidiki, antara lain sistem produksi yang ada, penerapan kompresi permukaan, perforasi zona reservoir tambahan, dan pengeboran sumur pengisian, dengan kinerja reservoir, keterkiriman sumur, dan perilaku jaringan produksi permukaan yang dianalisis menggunakan perangkat lunak simulasi MBAL, PROSPER, dan GAP. Konfigurasi lima sumur yang ada ditemukan mampu mempertahankan dataran tinggi hanya selama 4,49 tahun, hanya mewakili 28% dari target kontrak. Di antara skenario perforasi yang dinilai, konfigurasi yang menggunakan tabung 4 inci pada tekanan pemisah 725 psi menghasilkan hasil yang paling menguntungkan, memperpanjang durasi dataran tinggi selama 12,54 tahun, dari 6,24 tahun menjadi 18,78 tahun, menunjukkan potensi signifikan untuk mengakses lapisan produktif tambahan

Kata kunci: 3-5 optimasi produksi gas, penurunan tekanan reservoir, pemodelan produksi terintegrasi, kompresi permukaan, dan keberlanjutan produksi.

1. INTRODUCTION

Natural gas production declines as reservoir pressure depletes over time, reducing well deliverability and making it increasingly difficult to maintain gas production targets (Ahmed, 2019; Guo, 2011). Sustaining a stable production plateau is particularly important for gas fields operating under long-term Gas Sales Agreements, where failure to deliver the required gas rate can negatively affect project economics and supply reliability to the customers (Mucharam et al., 2007; Soemardan et al., 2013).

To mitigate production decline, the company employs various optimization strategies, including drilling infill wells, reservoir recompletion through perforation of additional productive layers, and gas compression (Montoya et al., 2018). However, selecting the most effective strategy requires a comprehensive understanding of the interactions between the reservoir, wellbore, and surface production system (Yu et al., 2024).

As reservoir pressure declines, production constraints may shorten the plateau period and limit the field's ability to satisfy contractual gas demand (Aliaga & Huerta, 2017; Wang, 2003). This study investigates production optimization options for a Mnazibay gas field targeting a production rate of 130 MMscfd over a 16-year production period. An integrated production system modelling approach is used to evaluate the effectiveness of gas compression, perforation of additional reservoir layers, and drilling of an infill well in extending the production plateau. Hence, production system optimization should be implemented from the initial stages of production to maintain reservoir performance and ensure that the target gas volumes are delivered in accordance with the agreed schedule (Aliaga & Huerta, 2017; Latif et al., 2019).

The study aims to identify the most effective optimization strategy to sustain gas production while maximizing recovery from the field. The findings provide practical guidance for managing mature gas reservoirs facing pressure depletion and production decline.

2. METHODOLOGY

The production system studied consists of five wells, reservoirs, and surface facilities of one of the gas fields located in the southern part of Tanzania. The IPM approach was used to evaluate production optimization strategies for the Mnazibay gas field. PVT was used to simulate the fluid, MBAL to represent the reservoir, and PROSPER and GAP were used to model the wells and surface equipment, respectively. Finally, a system with integrated GAP software was built. Below is an explanation of the simulation of each part, and the workflow for this research study can be explained through the flowchart in Figure 1.

Data gathering

The data employed to construct the Mnazibay gas field model for this study included fluid properties shown in Table 1. PVT data, such as water-to-gas ratio, water salinity, gas gravity, condensate-to-gas ratio, Water gas ratio, and Table 3 natural gas composition. Table 2 shows reservoir parameters of each layer, including temperature, reservoir pressure, porosity values, connate water, saturations, CGR, WGR, and IGIP. Gas production data covering the period from December 2016 to 2024 was utilized, along with data on well completion, wellbore radius, perforation intervals, well depths, and the diameters of tubing and casing.

Table 1. PVT data

Parameter	Amount
Reservoir Fluid	Gas
Tank Model	Single Tank
PVT Model	Simple PVT
CGR	0.08 STB/MMscf
Water Gas Ratio	0 STB/MMscf
Oil Gravity	25 API
Gas Gravity	0.56
Water Salinity	1000 ppm
Mole percent H ₂ S	0
Mole percent CO ₂	0.18%
Mole percent N ₂	0.18%

Development of the reservoir Model (MBAL) and History Matching

Based on available data, MBAL tank models are built to represent the geological understanding of the field. Each reservoir layer was presumed to be treated as an independent reservoir for the sake of simplicity, with the zones not interacting (IPM, 2019). The gas reservoir was classified as volumetric, characterized by a fixed volume of a closed gas reservoir and tank, devoid of external energy contributions, including the lack of water influx (Ahmed, 2019).

The reservoir was assumed to be governed by a depletion-drive mechanism, in which the expansion of the gas initially in place provides the primary source of energy for fluid flow as reservoir pressure declines from P_i to P (equation 3-1). (Baker, 2015; Singh et al., 2005)

History matching was conducted to achieve an accurate pressure match by adjusting the Gas Initially in Place (GIIP) of individual tanks and the transmissibility coefficients between the tanks. (James R. Gilman, 2013; Sallam & El-Banbi, 2018).

The history matching is informed by the GIIP obtained from P/Z (Okotie & Ikporo, 2018). The history-matched MBAL is subsequently utilized for the baseline production forecast.

Figure 1. Study Flow Diagram

Table 2. Reservoir Properties of the Layers

Layer	Reservoir Pressure (Psig)	Reservoir Temp (°F)	CGR STB/MMscf	WGR STB/MMscf	Oil gravity °API	Porosity fraction	Water sat	IGIP BCF
I	2887	160	0.075	0	25	0.14	0.31	129.45
H	2896	175	0.075	0	25	0.14	0.31	129.35
G	2900	180	0.075	0	25	0.20	0.32	100.00
F	2909	192	0.075	0	25	0.20	0.32	120.00
E	2931	210	0.075	0	25	0.15	0.22	122.00
D	2982	210	0.075	0	25	0.20	0.41	125.00
C	2993	210	0.075	0	25	0.16	0.44	125.00
K	2500	177	0.090	0	26	0.18	0.29	144.00

$$GB_{gi} = (G - G_p)B_g \quad 4-1$$

$$GB_g - GB_{gi} = G_p B_g \quad 4-2$$

Whereby;

$$B_{gi} = \frac{0.0283Z_i T_i}{P_i} \quad 4-3$$

$$B_g = \frac{0.0283ZT}{P} \quad 4-4$$

$$G \frac{0.0283Z_i T_i}{P_i} = (G - G_p) \frac{0.0283ZT}{P} \quad 4-5$$

$$G \frac{Z_i}{P_i} = (G - G_p) \frac{Z}{P} \quad 4-6$$

$$\frac{P}{Z} = \frac{P_i}{Z_i} \left(1 - \frac{G_p}{G} \right) \frac{P_i}{Z_i} \quad 4-7$$

Table 3. Natural gas composition

Composition	(Mole Fraction %)
H2	0.00
N2	0.18
CO2	0.18
H2S	0.00
C1	98.19
C2	1.01
C3	0.28
IC4	0.05
NC4	0.06
IC5	0.02
NC5	0.01

Development of Well Model (PROSPER)

All the wellbore models were developed using PROSPER. Production wellbore models were coupled to the reservoir or tank model. Properties of petroleum fluids, such as Fluid PVT data (Gas composition, Gas gravity, Z-factor, and viscosity correlation), Reservoir data, Well Geometry, well completion, and tubing data, are important parameters considered during the design and analysis of petroleum production systems.

In this software, PVT data were entered and compared with laboratory data. (Experts, 2010) The inflow performance relationship (IPR) and vertical lift performance (VLP) were developed by Petroleum experts-2 correlation (IPM, 2010).

Development of a Surface Facility Model (GAP).

The General Allocation Program was utilized to develop the production network for the Mnazibay gas field. The production network generated for the current production system (base case) is illustrated in Figure 2. Gap production network for the existing gas field. This network consists of reservoirs, wells, wellheads, manifolds, and separators. The Gap model integrates reservoir, well, and surface facility models to simulate steady-state production by balancing pressure, flow rate, and temperature throughout the production system. It uses inputs from reservoir and well models to predict production performance and optimize gas production under specified operational constraints.

Figure 2. Gap production network for the existing gas field.

Key data required for reliable network modelling include flowline length, elevation, diameter, wall thickness, roughness, and pipeline interconnections (Almohammad & Al-Saqabi, 2016). The solver accounts for all the physics present in the system and operates

by extracting information from all components and performing dynamic calculations on the physical models, such as pipelines, chokes, wells, and compressors.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Four cases, with different scenarios, were simulated. These cases are the current field development configuration, surface compression, perforating new layers, and infill drilling. The results provide insights into system behaviour and identify effective approaches for sustaining plateau production as required in the 16-year gas sales agreement

Case 1. Base case field development scenario

The base case is the current field development configuration, as modelled in the GAP-integrated surface network. The producing system includes five vertical wells, MB-1, MB-2, MB-3, MB-4, and MS-1X, completed in various reservoir layers, called Layers D, F, G, E, and K, respectively, as shown in Figure 2. These wells have a common flow to a surface gathering system, which conveys fluids by a trunk line to a three-phase separator operating at a pressure of 1,450 psi, and production tubing of 2.876 inches in diameter for all wells.

The results from GAP simulation for the base case demonstrate that the five-well system can sustain the target plateau production rate of 130 MMscf/d from the field start date of 31 December 2016 until June 2021, corresponding to a plateau duration of 4.49 years and a recovery factor of 69%, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Production Gas Rate and Recovery Factor for Case 1

The findings from the base case 1 demonstrate that the existing five-well configuration is incapable of meeting the 16-year plateau obligation specified in the GSA to sustain the

required gas production constraint of 130 MMscfd over the long term due to continuous reservoir pressure decline, as shown in Figure 2. The plateau shortfall amounts to 11.5 years, representing a critical gap that requires a field development intervention, including installing a compression system, drilling additional wells, and perforating additional layers.

Case 2. Effect of using a surface compressor.

Figure 3 illustrates the adjusted Case 1 model, which incorporates a compressor into the surface network system. This modification was implemented following Case 1 inability to reach the production plateau as of June 31, 2021.

The findings show that the compressor extended the plateau production period by an additional 3.51 years. As a result, the total plateau duration increased from 4.49 years in the base case to 8 years in the compressor-assisted case as shown by Figure 5. **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 4. Application of Compressor System-GAP Model for Case 2

However, although the compressor considerably improved production performance, it was not sufficient on its own to achieve the 16-year plateau period required by the Gas Sales Agreement GSA. Nevertheless, the results clearly demonstrate that compression is an effective method for delaying production decline and improving field deliverability during the later stages of reservoir depletion.

Figure 5. Production profile for the Compressor Application

The findings show that the recovery factor increased from 75% in the base case to 85% in the compressor-assisted case. This improvement suggests that additional gas reserves, which would otherwise remain unrecovered due to pressure constraints within the production system, were successfully produced after the compressor was installed.

Case 3. Effects of increasing the perforated zones.

The addition of three new reservoir layers or zones, Layers C, I, and H, was connected to the existing production system, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Gap production network with added layers/zones for the gas field

The results from the simulation plot Figure 7 show that for the 2.867-inch tubing with a separator pressure of 725 psi, the plateau length increased from 4.49 years to 13.57 years, representing a net gain of 9.08 years. Similarly, at a separator pressure of 1450 psi, the plateau length increased from 2.30 years to 8.80 years, yielding an improvement of 6.50 years.

The most significant enhancement was observed for the 4-inch tubing at 725 psi, where the plateau period increased from 6.24 years to 18.78 years, corresponding to a net gain of 12.54 years. For the 4-inch tubing at 1450 psi, the plateau length increased from 4.24 years to 12.57 years, resulting in an extension of 8.33 years, which is further summarized in Table 4 and Figure 8

Table 4. Effect of Additional Perforated Layers on Plateau Duration Under Different Tubing Diameters and Separator Pressures

condition	2.867inch	2.867inch	4inch	4inch
	725psia	1450psia	725psia	1450psia
Before adding layers(years)	4.49	2.3	6.24	4.24
After adding layers(years)	13.57	8.8	18.78	12.57
Net Effect (years)	9.08	6.5	12.54	8.33

Figure 7. Effect of tubing size and separator pressure

Figure 8. Effect of adding reservoir layers/zones.

Case 4: Infill Well Development Scenarios.

In this case, five new wells were incrementally added to the GAP model, with each case adding one well. The modified network illustrated in Figure 8 contains five new well sources, MB-5, MB-6, MB-7, MB-8, and MB-9, attached to three new reservoir layers named as Layers C, I, and H.

Figure 9. Expanded GAP network model incorporating five infill wells.

Five incremental infill scenarios were evaluated in sequence, with wells added one at a time from a single-well infill case through to the full five-well programme, to characterise the marginal contribution of each additional well to the plateau extension objective

Figure 10 and Figure 11 both illustrate the effect, which is further summarized in Table 5. Effect of infilling a new well in the production plateau.. According to these findings, infill new has the effect of increasing the capacity of the gas production system.

Figure 10. Effect of new infill wells on production

Table 5. Effect of infilling a new well in the production plateau.

Scenarios	Infill Wells	Total Wells	Plateau Duration (years)	Net Extension (years)	GSA Compliance (16 years)
Base (Case 1)	0	5	4.49	—	Not Met
Case 4a	1	6	10	+5.51	Not Met
Case 4b	2	7	11.25	+6.67	Not Met
Case 4c	3	8	14.25	+9.67	Not Met
Case 4d	4	9	16.00	+11.51	Met
Case 4e	5	10	17.50	+13.01	Met

Figure 11. Effect of infilling a new well

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the result, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- i. The existing five-well field configuration sustains the 130 MMscf/d production plateau for only 4.49 years, which is equivalent to 28% of the 16-year contractual target.
- ii. The optimum approach was identified as the one that provided the greatest extension of the production plateau period.
- iii. Among all the perforated evaluated scenarios, the 4-inch tubing at a separator pressure of 725 psi provided the most favourable outcome. The plateau duration increased by 12.54 years, from 6.24 years to 18.78 years, highlighting the substantial benefit of incorporating the additional layers.
- iv. Case 4d found that the addition of four new wells into the existing field increased the plateau duration to 16 years. These cases reach the 16-year contractual target of field production, therefore identified as the optimal optimization scenario for field compliance.

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